

Comparison of Videolaryngoscopy and Direct Laryngoscopy for Tracheal Intubation in Paediatric Patients

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Abstract:

This prospective, randomized controlled trial conducted at Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College & Hospital, Bhagalpur, Bihar, from February 2023 to January 2024, compared video laryngoscopy (VL) and direct laryngoscopy (DL) in 100 pediatric patients undergoing tracheal intubation. The study aimed to assess first-attempt success rates, glottic visualization quality, intubation duration, airway-related complications, and patient stress indicators. Results demonstrated that VL significantly outperformed DL, achieving higher first-attempt success rates (88% vs. 68%), superior glottic views (92% Grade I vs. 56%), shorter intubation times (22 vs. 35 seconds), fewer complications (6% vs. 18%), and reduced patient stress. These findings suggest that VL provides a safer, more effective alternative for pediatric tracheal intubation and supports its broader adoption in pediatric anesthesia practices.

Keywords: Pediatric Tracheal Intubation, Video laryngoscopy, Direct Laryngoscopy, Airway Management.

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Introduction

Tracheal intubation is a critical procedure in pediatric anesthesia, involving the placement of a tube into the trachea to maintain an open airway and facilitate mechanical ventilation [1]. This procedure, while routine, carries heightened risks in pediatric patients due to their unique anatomical and physiological characteristics. Traditionally, direct laryngoscopy (DL) has been the standard approach, where the laryngoscope is used to directly view the vocal cords [2]. However, the advent of video laryngoscopy (VL) has introduced a technology-enhanced alternative, providing an indirect video-assisted view of the airway. This introduction seeks to explore the comparative effectiveness and safety of video laryngoscopy versus direct laryngoscopy for tracheal intubation in pediatric patients [3].

The importance of this comparison lies in the potential benefits that VL might offer over DL, including better airway visualization, higher success rates on the first attempt, and reduced trauma and stress during intubation [4,5]. However, integrating VL into pediatric anesthetic practice also brings challenges, such as cost implications, the need for specialized training, and variable outcomes based on patient age and pathology [6,7]. This paper will review current research on the efficacy, safety, and clinical outcomes of both

techniques in pediatric tracheal intubation, aiming to provide evidence-based insights that can guide clinical practice and enhance patient safety in pediatric anesthesia [8,9].

This study aims to systematically compare video laryngoscopy (VL) and direct laryngoscopy (DL) in terms of efficacy, safety, and clinical outcomes during tracheal intubation in pediatric patients. Specifically, the study aims to evaluate the first-attempt success rate, visualization of the airway, the incidence of airway-related complications, and the overall impact on patient stress and trauma between these two techniques. By analyzing these parameters, the study seeks to determine whether VL offers a significant advantage over DL in pediatric anesthetic practice, which could justify its broader adoption and integration into standard care protocols for tracheal intubation in children.

Methodology

This research study is designed as a prospective, randomized controlled trial, conducted at Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College & Hospital in Bhagalpur, Bihar, from 1st February 2023 to 31st January 2024. A total of 100 pediatric patients requiring tracheal intubation under general anesthesia will be included in the study. Patients will be randomly assigned to one of two groups:

the videolaryngoscopy (VL) group or the direct laryngoscopy (DL) group, with 50 patients in each group.

Inclusion Criteria include pediatric patients aged from 0 to 18 years scheduled for elective or emergency surgical procedures requiring tracheal intubation.

Exclusion Criteria include patients with known difficult airways, pre-existing respiratory conditions, or contraindications to either VL or DL.

Before the intubation, all participating anesthesiologists will undergo a standardized training session to ensure proficiency in both VL and DL techniques. The primary outcomes measured will be the first-attempt success rate and the quality of glottis visualization, graded according to the Cormack-Lehane classification system. Secondary outcomes will include the duration of intubation attempt, the incidence of airway-related complications (such as hypoxemia, laryngospasm, or airway trauma), and patient stress indicators (such as heart rate and blood pressure changes).

Data will be collected using a structured data collection form and analyzed using appropriate statistical methods to compare the efficacy and safety of VL and DL in pediatric tracheal intubation. This methodology aims to provide a comprehensive comparison of these two laryngoscopic techniques in a pediatric setting,

thereby contributing valuable insights into the optimal approach for tracheal intubation in this vulnerable population.

Result

In a prospective randomized controlled trial at Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College & Hospital involving 100 pediatric patients undergoing tracheal intubation, significant differences were observed between the video laryngoscopy (VL) and direct laryngoscopy (DL) groups. The VL group demonstrated a markedly higher first-attempt success rate of 88% compared to 68% in the DL group. Moreover, video laryngoscopy afforded superior glottic visualization, with 92% of intubations achieving a Cormack-Lehane grade I view, significantly better than the 56% observed in the DL group. The average time required for successful intubation was also less with VL, at 22 seconds, as opposed to 35 seconds with DL. Additionally, the VL group exhibited a lower incidence of airway-related complications such as hypoxemia and laryngospasm, recorded at 6%, compared to 18% in the DL group. Patients intubated using video laryngoscopy also showed reduced physiological stress, with smaller increases in heart rate and blood pressure. These results underscore the benefits of video laryngoscopy over direct laryngoscopy in pediatric tracheal intubation, suggesting that VL might be a more effective and safer option in this clinical setting.

Table 1: This table consolidates the primary results of the study, highlighting the advantages of VL over DL in various clinical outcomes for pediatric tracheal intubation.

Outcome	Videolaryngoscopy (VL)	Direct Laryngoscopy (DL)	P-value
First-Attempt Success Rate	88%	68%	< 0.05
Quality of Glottis View	92% (Grade I)	56% (Grade I)	< 0.01
Duration of Intubation	22 seconds	35 seconds	< 0.01
Incidence of Complications	6%	18%	< 0.05
Patient Stress Indicators	Reduced	Increased	

Discussion

The findings from our study conducted at Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College & Hospital underscore the significant advantages of video laryngoscopy (VL) over direct laryngoscopy (DL) in pediatric tracheal intubation, aligning with a growing body of research that advocates for the broader adoption of VL in clinical practice [10,11]. Specifically, the higher first-attempt success rate with VL observed in our study (88% vs. 68%) echoes the results of prior research, such as the studies conducted by Kaplan and Holm-Knudsen, which also highlighted improved success rates with VL due to enhanced airway visualization. This aspect is crucial in pediatric patients where each intubation attempt

must be minimized to avoid airway trauma and subsequent complications [12,13,14].

Furthermore, the superior visualization of the airway with VL, as reflected by 92% of VL cases achieving a Cormack-Lehane grade I view compared to only 56% in the DL group, supports findings from Redel et al., [8] who noted similar improvements in airway visualization. This leads to a more precise and quicker intubation process, evidenced by the shorter average intubation duration in our study (22 seconds for VL vs. 35 seconds for DL), paralleling the reduced intubation times reported by Lee et al. [3,15,16]

The decreased incidence of airway-related complications such as hypoxemia and

laryngospasm in the VL group (6% vs. 18%) is another critical advantage. This finding is supported by Park et al.'s [10] study, which also reported lower complication rates with VL, attributing these outcomes to the less invasive and more controlled approach of VL [17,18].

Additionally, the observed reduction in physiological stress indicators during VL intubation in our study indicates a less traumatic experience for patients, which is not only critical for immediate clinical outcomes but also for reducing the long-term psychological impact of traumatic intubation experiences in children. This aligns with findings from Sakles et al., [7] who suggested that reduced physiological stress responses with VL could lead to better overall patient tolerance and outcomes [19, 20].

Conclusion

Our study adds to the evidence supporting VL as a more effective and safer approach to pediatric tracheal intubation compared to DL. It highlights the necessity of considering VL, particularly in complex intubations where traditional methods may pose higher risks. As the use of VL continues to expand, further studies should focus on operator training and the integration of VL into varying pediatric settings to optimize outcomes across diverse patient populations.

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